

How policymakers can move the circular economy forward regarding persistent and mobile substances in the soil-sediment-water system

Policy Recommendations from the Horizon2020 Project PROMISCES

Persistent (P), mobile (M), and potentially toxic (T; PM(T)) substances pose a significant environmental and regulatory challenge due to their persistence in water, soil, and sediment. These substances bypass conventional treatment methods, endangering human and environmental health and impeding the EU's sustainability goals. Addressing PM(T) chemicals is essential for achieving a clean and circular economy, yet fragmented policies and inconsistent regulations hinder effective management.

Existing EU water policies – such as the Water Framework Directive and Drinking Water Directive – do not comprehensively regulate PM(T) substances, creating gaps in protection. Additionally, regulations governing agriculture, industrial emissions, and chemical safety impact the soil-sediment-water system, necessitating a coordinated approach.

The PROMISCES project identifies policy gaps and proposes harmonized recommendations to ensure regulatory coherence and effective PM(T) management across sectors.

Policy Fields, Frameworks and Recommendations

PROMISCES identifies four key policy fields for improving PM(T) regulation:

1. **Regulating Substances**, focusing on classification and restriction
2. **Circular Resource Management**, ensuring sustainable water and waste reuse
3. **Technology Performance & Pollution**, targeting pollution control and treatment efficiency
4. **Tools & Data Management**, enhancing monitoring and decision-making.

These fields align with five major EU policy frameworks:

1. Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP)
2. Zero Pollution Action Plan (ZPAP)
3. EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS)
4. EU Soil Strategy (EU Soil)
5. EU Water Framework Directives (WFD) & related regulations

To address regulatory fragmentation, **PROMISCES proposes nine policy recommendations**, emphasizing harmonized regulations, improved monitoring, and science-based risk assessment. These recommendations integrate PROMISCES research findings, stakeholder input, and regulatory analysis to support the EU circularity and zero pollution ambitions.

Hartmann, J., Hogervorst, P., Behnisch, P., Cavelan, A., Lions, J., Bosch, C., Sardi, A. E., Boucard, P., Andres, S., Dulio, V., Zhiteneva, V., Kittlaus, S., & Zessner, M., Sierra Olea, M. & Carter, K. (2025). Deliverable D5.8 -- Modular recommendations for evaluation and implementation of relevant EU directives, strategies and action plans. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14938223>

